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Evaluation of sparse data storage on complex and moving domains

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Chapter

1

Introduction

In this deliverable, we show the capability of the implemented sparse data structure for complex domains. Further, we explain the benefits of a hybrid data structure, that can decide about a sparse or dense data structure per block, based on the porosity of the block. This results in the best possible performance and memory consumption for every block. We present a simulation of an artificial riverbed, where the hybrid data structure is very beneficial. Further, we show the benefits of the sparse data structure with a blood flow simulation through a sparse artery.

In the second part of this deliverable, we present the integration of the Partially Saturated Cells Method (PSM) into *lbmpy*, which enables the WALBERLA framework to handle complex moving domains. We present, how to move/rotate a complex geometry efficiently, and we show node-level performance analysis on CPU and GPU. Lastly, to test the capability of the implementation of the PSM combined with the rotation module, we run a big industrial use case, a counter-rotating open rotor simulation.

Sparse data structure for complex domains

2.1 Dynamic block structure

In Figure 2.1 we can see, how the generated sparse LBM kernel performs against the generated dense kernel. On the y-axis, the mega fluid lattice updates per second (MFLUPs) are presented, on the x-axis, the porosity $\phi = \frac{N_F}{N}$ is shown. The LB method uses a D3Q19 velocity set and SRT collision operator. The benchmark runs only the LBM kernel and is performed on an NVIDIA A100 GPU.

First of all, we can observe, that the single GPU performance of the sparse kernel is quite close to the theoretical performance. Furthermore, the MFLUPs performance is quite stable for decreasing porosity.

But Figure 2.1 also shows, that the sparse kernels perform worse for $\phi \geq 0.8$. This is, because of the extra memory accesses of the sparse data structure. While a dense kernel accesses $2Q \cdot \text{size}(pdf)$ bytes per cell on GPUs, the sparse kernel accesses $2Q \cdot \text{size}(pdf) + (Q - 1) \cdot \text{size}(index)$ bytes per cell, because it needs to read neighboring information from the `index-list`.

On the other side, the performance for the dense kernel linearly decreases for decreasing porosity. The reason for this behavior is, that dense kernels in WALBERLA run over all cells of the block, including non-fluid cells, which avoids the need for a branch condition for non-fluid cells, but this of course linearly decreases the fluid lattice updates per second.

As indicated in Figure 2.1, the break-even point for sparse and dense kernels is at $\phi \sim 0.8$. If we think about applications like porous media or artery setups, where some blocks are full of fluid cells, while other blocks primarily consist of non-fluid cells, both data structures do not seem to fit the given domain structure.

Therefore, we implemented the possibility to run hybrid data structure simulations in WALBERLA. From *lbmpy*, sparse and dense LBM and boundary kernels are created. In WALBERLA, the porosity ϕ is calculated on each block, and then this block is marked with a `block state` as a sparse or dense block, based on a porosity switch parameter ϕ_S , which could be for example $\phi_S = 0.8$. Then, at the creation of the data structures on the blocks, the `block state` decides, if a dense PDF field or the `PDF-list` and `index-list` is created on the block. The `block state` also decides, which type of kernel runs on the block.

The only tricky thing then is the communication between sparse and dense blocks. Therefore, *lbmpy* was extended to support the generation of specific pack and unpack kernels for CPU or GPU architectures, while the actual MPI communication routine stayed unchanged.

In Figure 2.1, we can see the hybrid data structure in green with $\phi_S = 0.8$. As expected, the performance mirrors that of the dense kernel for $\phi \geq \phi_S$, and afterward that of the sparse kernel. So by this hybrid approach, we can always reach the maximum possible WALBERLA performance per block, independent of the porosity.

We can also calculate the theoretical memory consumption of the sparse and dense data structures, as done in Figure 2.2. We can obtain, that the memory consumption of the sparse LBM is higher for $\phi_S > 0.66$. This is, because of the extra storage of the `index list`. We have to store a pull index for every PDF, so if the PDF needs 8 Bytes (double) and the pull index is a 4 Byte integer, the memory consumption here is 50% percent higher for a domain with only fluid cells. But this extra memory consumption plays less role for decreasing porosity values, as we only store fluid cells. The dense LBM on the other side stores all kinds of cells, and has therefore the same memory consumption for the whole porosity range, which makes the sparse data structure

beneficial in terms of memory for $\phi_S < 0.66$. Again, the hybrid data structure can be utilized to minimize memory consumption based on the block porosity.

Figure 2.1: Single GPU benchmark for sparse, dense and hybrid data structure with varying porosity on an NVIDIA A100 with 256^3 cells, D3Q19 velocity set and SRT collision operator. The theoretical performances is calculated from the bandwidth of a streaming benchmark (1361 GB/s) and the theoretical number of memory accesses of the kernels, as LBM code is usually memory bound.

2.2 Applications

In Figure 2.3 the LAGOON test case is presented. The simulation is run with sparse blocks only, as it was already done in deliverable 5.2. So the newly implemented sparse data structure is capable of running a highly turbulent, high parallel complex geometry case on a high number of CPUs or GPUs. Nevertheless, as the domain mainly consists of fluid cells, the sparse data structure holds no benefit for this test case. The performance is lower than that of the dense data structure, as shown in Figure 2.1, as the porosity on all blocks is close to 1.0.

For testing the hybrid data structure, we created an artificial riverbed, as shown in Figure 2.4. The particles in this test case are fixed, so this is still a static complex geometry test case. As we can see in Figure 2.4, the upper part of the simulation domain only consists of fluid flowing over particles. In this part of the domain, only fluid cells are present, and the block porosity is 1.0. That means, that the dense data structure is more valuable on these blocks. In the lower part, the area is dominated by particles, which means a lot of boundary cells. The block porosity in the lower part of the domain is between 0.4 and 0.6. This means, that when using the sparse data structure on these blocks, we can increase performance according to Figure 2.1 and reduce memory according to Figure 2.2. So for this complex test case, the feature of being able to decide over the data storage per block is very useful to achieve good performance and memory consumption for every part of the domain.

Another complex geometry test case is the blood flow in an artery as shown in Figure 2.5. One can see, that only a very small part of the simulation domain consists of fluid cells, the rest is boundary. To reduce the number of boundary cells in the domain, we choose a small number of cells per block, which results in a high number of blocks with boundary cells only, which then can be omitted. Nevertheless, the remaining blocks have a wide range of porosities, ranging from 0.01 to 1.0, with an average of only 0.15 percent of fluid cells per block. This means, that the sparse data structure is again highly valuable for this complex geometry simulation.

In general, we can show a good theoretical performance for the sparse test cases before. The sparse data structure is well suited for complex geometry simulations with a high percentage of boundary cells in the

Figure 2.2: Theoretical memory consumption of sparse vs dense data structure depending on the porosity

domain such as porous media flows, and simulations in very sparse domains such as the artery in Figure 2.5. By implementing the hybrid data structure approach presented in section 2.1, the range of useful applications increased, as the riverbed test case of Figure 2.4 shows.

Nevertheless, only the LAGOON test case was part of the SCALABLE project, so we had a chance to look deeper into the actual performance of this case (see deliverable 5.2). As the other two cases were not part of SCALABLE work packages, there was no time for the evaluation of the performance on HPC systems. But as already mentioned, Figure 2.1 can give us a good hint. Nevertheless, factors like the block decomposition and the resulting communication routines are not captured by the theoretical performance of the sparse kernel.

Figure 2.3: LAGOON test case visualized by Q-criterion. Grey lines indicate domain decomposition into sparse blocks

Figure 2.4: Riverbed velocity profile. Grey mesh indicates dense blocks, black mesh indicates sparse blocks

Figure 2.5: Domain decomposition of blood vessels. Black mesh indicates sparse WALBERLA blocks

Complex moving domains

Before the start of the SCALABLE project, WALBERLA was not capable of running simulations with moving complex geometries. Therefore we extended the framework to enable this feature by exploiting the PSM method. The goal is to run the SCALABLE counter-rotating open rotor (CROR) industrial test case efficiently on a high number of CPUs and GPUs.

3.1 PSM theory

The partially saturated cells method (PSM) is usually used for fluid-particle implementation with geometrically resolved particles ([6], [3]). Due to its similarities to pure LBM and therefore its highly parallel nature, it is already successfully utilized for running on GPUs ([3], [1]). A special benefit of the PSM is, that there are no explicit boundary kernels, but the no-slip boundary on the object surface is integrated in the LBM step. The classical lattice Boltzmann equation reads

$$f_i(\mathbf{x} + \mathbf{c}_i, t + 1) = f_i(\mathbf{x}, t) + \Omega_i^F(\mathbf{x}, t), \quad (3.1)$$

with for example the fluid SRT collision operator

$$\Omega_i^F(\mathbf{x}, t) = -\frac{1}{\tau}(f_i(\mathbf{x}, t) - f_i^{(eq)}(\mathbf{x}, t)) \quad (3.2)$$

and

$$f_i^{(eq)}(\mathbf{u}, \rho) = \omega_i \rho \left[1 + \left(\frac{\mathbf{c}_i \cdot \mathbf{u}}{c_s^2} + \frac{(\mathbf{c}_i \cdot \mathbf{u})^2}{2c_s^4} + \frac{\mathbf{u}^2}{2c_s^2} \right) \right] \quad (3.3)$$

The classical lattice Boltzmann equation can be extended by a solid collision operator Ω_i^S and a solid volume fraction field $B(\mathbf{x}, t)$ to result in

$$f_i(\mathbf{x} + \mathbf{c}_i, t + 1) = f_i(\mathbf{x}, t) + (1 - B(\mathbf{x}, t)) \cdot \Omega_i^F(\mathbf{x}, t) + B(\mathbf{x}, t) \cdot \Omega_i^S(\mathbf{x}, t). \quad (3.4)$$

The solid volume fraction $B(\mathbf{x}, t)$ is a field indicating the presence or absence of an object in a specific cell. For cells with no object the solid volume fraction is 0, for a cell completely inside an object, it is 1, and for a cell at the interface of the object and the fluid, the fraction is between 0 and 1. We will see in [subsection 3.2.2](#), how to efficiently build and modify this volume fraction field for a moving geometry over time.

According to [2] the solid collision operator $\Omega_i^S(\mathbf{x}, i)$ can have three different appearances, but we will only use

$$\Omega_i^S(\mathbf{x}, i) = [f_{\bar{i}}(\mathbf{x}, t) - f_{\bar{i}}^{(eq)}(\rho, \mathbf{u})] - [f_i(\mathbf{x}, t) - f_i^{(eq)}(\rho, \mathbf{u}_s)] \quad (3.5)$$

with \bar{i} as the opposite PDF direction of i and \mathbf{u}_s as the velocity of the solid volume.

As we can see, the no-slip bounce-back boundary kernel is integrated into the LBM formulation by the solid collision operator Ω^S . Therefore, no extra boundary kernel call is necessary, which is especially beneficial for GPU runs, where an extra kernel call can reduce performance.

However, the greater advantage of the PSM is the absence of a need for PDF reconstruction. Usually, when running LBM simulations with moving solid volumes such as particles, a cell, where there was a solid volume covering the cell, the cell holds no valid PDF values. So when the solid volume moves away from the cell, it becomes a fluid cell and its PDF needs to be reconstructed by some reconstruction procedure. This can be

costly, can cause instabilities, and is very hard to program effectively on accelerators. As already mentioned, the PSM on the other hand is because of its parallel nature well suited for processing on accelerators like NVIDIA or AMD GPUs.

However, the PSM can not only be used for fluid-particle interaction. The authors of [5], [4] and [2] show, that the PSM is suitable for all fluid-structure interactions, such as moving or rotation obstacles such as the Counter Rotation Open Rotor (CROR) test case presented in subsection 3.3.2.

3.2 PSM in waLBerla

3.2.1 The PSM method in *lbmpy*

To integrate the PSM in the code generation, some changes to *lbmpy* needed to be made. First of all, a new class called `PSM_Config` is integrated, which holds some symbolic fields such as the solid volume fraction field, the object velocity field, or the object force field needed for the fluid particle interaction. It also decides on the options of the PSM, such as the choice of one of the three solid collision operators described in [2]. Next, a function is implemented to append the solid collision to the collision assignment, which was previously built for a pure LBM collision. Lastly, the terms for the fluid collision and the forcing term are adapted by multiplying $(1 - B(\mathbf{x}, t))$, to receive Equation 3.4.

By integrating the PSM into the code generation, we can now run fluid-particle or moving geometry simulations with all kinds of collision operators (SRT, TRT, MRT, central moments, cumulants, ...), stencils (D2Q9, D3Q19, D3Q27, ...) and all other functionalities of *lbmpy* and *pystencils* such as turbulence models, various streaming pattern (pull, aa, esotwist) or code vectorization.

3.2.2 Efficient creation and modification of the solid volume fraction field for a complex geometry

A big challenge for the integration of complex moving geometries in WALBERLA was the creation and modification of the solid volume fraction field $B(\mathbf{x}, t)$ in time. If the geometry can be described analytically, which is the case for a sphere or a cylinder, one can redo the mapping of the object onto the solid volume fraction field in the LBM grid dimension very efficiently. But if the geometry is complex, which means, that it can not be described by basic shapes, then the mapping is not straightforward. Usually, a complex geometry is described by a high number of vertices and faces and comes in a storage format like STL or object file. One target geometry for the SCALABLE project is the CROR geometry shown in Figure 3.2. Here the fine structure of the mesh can be seen, which consists of 610,692 vertices and 1,221,380 faces. As the number of vertices and faces is that high, there is no real option to efficiently rotate the vertices and then map/voxelize the geometry onto the fraction field every time step. Even by using accelerator data structures such as the distance-octree, the voxelization can not be done faster than < 0.1 s, which would drastically reduce the overall performance of the LBM solver. Therefore, we used another approach inspired by [7]. Here, the complex geometry is voxelized only once onto a geometry field. This geometry field can have the same grid spacing as the LBM fields, or lower, which then results in some sort of super-sampling approach. Further, it can be stored as a bit-map (cell inside or outside the geometry) or can hold a solid volume fraction itself. By these parameters, one can tune the representation of the geometry in the LBM simulation. An example of an artificial geometry field is presented in Figure 3.1, where the geometry field of a oval geometry with a mesh spacing of $dx_{geo} = \frac{dx_{lbm}}{2}$ (super-sampling depth = 1) is shown.

After creating the geometry field, the solid volume fraction field is achieved by interpolation of the geometry field. The interpolation has the size of $(2^{super-sampling-depth} + 1)^3$, so for a super-sampling depth of 0 ($dx_{geo} = dx_{lbm}$), the interpolation stencil has the size $2 \times 2 \times 2$, and for a super-sampling depth of 2, the stencil would be $5 \times 5 \times 5$. So to get the solid volume fraction value of a specific cell, first the cell center of this cell in domain coordinates has to be calculated. Next, the cell center is mapped into the geometry field space. Here it will land in a cell of the geometry field, and then the interpolation stencil comes in place to interpolate over the neighborhood of this cell. Lastly, the interpolated fraction value is just written back to the solid volume fraction field $B(\mathbf{x}, t)$.

The rotation or translation of the object is achieved by the mapping into the geometry space. This is done by multiplying the cell center in LBM space with a rotation matrix or adding some translation vector, to get

the translated/rotated cell in geometry space. By this technique, no field or geometry has to be rotated, but only the mapping from LBM to geometry space is modified.

For GPU runs, the geometry field is filled once on CPU and then copied to the GPU. The actual interpolation kernel, which builds the solid volume fraction field from the geometry field every time step is fully executed on the GPU and is written as a CUDA kernel.

Figure 3.1: Super-sampled geometry field for a oval shape with super-sampling depth of 1.

Figure 3.2: Counter rotating open rotor geometry with 610,692 vertices and 1,221,380 faces. The front rotor rotating clockwise, while the back rotor (stator) rotating counter-clockwise.

3.3 Benchmark results

3.3.1 Node level performance

CPU performance

To test the performance of the rotation kernel and the PSM in general, we run some node-level benchmarks. We started with a CPU node level run on LUMI-C on one CPU node. The main CPU node of LUMI-C consists of 2x AMD EPYC 7763 (2.45 GHz base, 3.5 GHz boost) with 64 cores each, so 128 cores per node. We tested two scenarios on this architecture, first a rotating geometry over the whole domain, as shown in Figure 3.3a, and second a rotating geometry in a small part of the domain, as shown in Figure 3.5b, which is closer the SCALABLE CROR test case setup in subsection 3.3.2. Both scenarios are separated into 128 blocks of 64^3 cells per block so that one core holds one block.

In Figure 3.4 we can see the performance of different types of kernels for both scenarios. The baseline is the LBM-only kernel, which iterates over the whole domain and achieves a performance of 4.69 MLUPS per core for both scenarios, which makes sense, as both domains have the same size, and boundaries are ignored in this kernel. The second bar shows the performance of the LBM kernel plus the boundary kernel for the so-slip boundaries of the geometries. Here, the boundary kernel of scenario A takes 1.78% of the run time, while for scenario B, the boundary kernel takes only 0.05% percent. This of course makes sense, as scenario A consists of more boundary cells.

Next, we look at the PSM kernel explained in section 3.1, where fluid and boundary cells are both handled in only one kernel. Again, it makes sense, that the performance of 4.33 MLUPS per core is the same for both scenarios, as the number of boundary cells in the domain has no influence on the number of calculations or memory accesses of the kernel. Nevertheless, the performance of the PSM kernel is about 13% lower than the LBM kernel. This is because of the extra memory accesses for the solid volume fraction field as well as of the object velocity field for the solid collision term in Equation 3.5.

We can avoid some of these extra calculations and memory accesses by only evaluating the solid collision part at cells, where the solid volume fraction is > 0.0 . For this, we generated two collision rules in *lbmpy*, one for LBM only and one for the PSM, and we combined them by a condition depending on the solid volume fraction. We can obtain in the 4th bar of Figure 3.4, that this condition heavily influences the performance of the kernel, especially for scenario B, where there are very few cells with a solid volume fraction > 0.0 in the domain. This means, that mostly a pure LBM kernel is running on the cells, and therefore, the performance of the PSM + condition is with 4.60 MLUPS per core nearly at the same level as the LBM-only kernel.

Lastly, we look at the performance of the PSM with an actual rotating geometry. All previous kernels did not deal with rotation at all. The rotation is dealt with by building a new solid volume fraction field $B(\mathbf{x}, t)$ from the geometry field every time step as explained in subsection 3.2.2. As the geometry field is built in a pre-processing step, only the interpolation of the geometry field to the solid volume fraction field $B(\mathbf{x}, t)$ is performance-relevant. Here, we have to differentiate between different super-sampling depths, which lead to different interpolation stencil sizes, and therefore more memory accesses. In Figure 3.4 it is shown, that the rotation (interpolation) kernel has only a minor influence on the overall performance of the simulation. Especially for scenario B, the rotation takes less than 3% of the run time. It also seems that the super-sampling depth has no big influence on the performance, as even for a super-sampling depth of 3, which results in an interpolation stencil of $9 \times 9 \times 9$, the interpolation kernel took only 2.78% of the run time. We see another picture for scenario A. Here the geometry field fills the whole domain, therefore also the interpolation from the geometry field to the solid volume fraction field takes place in every cell of the domain. For a super-sampling depth of 0, the interpolation kernel took 21.92% of the wall time, and for a super-sampling depth of 1, the rotation took 27.19% of the run time. Nevertheless, scenario A is a worst-case scenario, where the geometry rotates over the whole domain, and still the performance is not dominated by the rotation kernel. For the industrial application in subsection 3.3.2, the domain setup is close to scenario B (see Figure 3.3b), therefore, the performance loss because of the rotation kernel always stays below 3% of the run time.

GPU performance

For a GPU node-level performance, we benchmarked the two scenarios on one JUWELS-Booster node, which consists of four NVIDIA A100 GPUs. As shown in Figure 3.5, we decomposed the domain into four blocks with 256^3 cells per block, so one block per GPU.

Figure 3.3: Block structure with 128 blocks for CPU node level performance on LUMI-C, 64^3 cells per block

Figure 3.4: Node level performance of PSM vs LBM on LUMI-C (2x AMD EPYC 7763) with 128 cores/blocks (64^3 cells per block). The two scenarios are shown in Figure 3.3

The node level performance results on the NVIDIA A100 node is shown in Figure 3.6. Again, the LBM-only kernel is the baseline with 4246.42 MLUPS per GPU for both scenarios. We also see that the boundary kernel for a higher number of boundaries has more influence on the performance on GPUs, the boundary kernel for scenario A takes 4.28% of the run time. Comparable to the CPU, the PSM kernel is also around 8% slower than the LBM kernel, which again comes from the extra memory accesses of the solid collision term. Again, the condition can reduce the performance penalty of the solid collision term, as it is only evaluated on cells with $B(\mathbf{x}, t) > 0.0$.

The rotation kernel for scenario B with 3.87% of the run time for both super-sampling depths was a bit slower than the same kernel on the CPU, which could result from a higher overhead of a kernel start on GPUs. The rotation kernel for scenario A on the other hand took only 9.79% percent of the run time for super-sampling of 0 and 12.92% for super-sampling of 1. Therefore, it took only half the overall run time as the same kernels on the CPU.

Overall, the node-level performance results show, that there is no big performance penalty in using the PSM for complex moving geometries. Also, the updating of the fraction field in every time step is implemented efficiently, so that even for the worst case scenario A it took less than 30% of the run time, and for the CROR test case setup it needs less than 4% of the runtime. This holds for the CPU as well as for the GPU implementation.

Figure 3.5: Block structure with 4 blocks for GPU node level performance on 4 NVIDIA A100 GPUs, 256^3 cells per block

Figure 3.6: Node level performance of PSM vs LBM on NVIDIA A100 (JUWELS-Booster) with 4 GPUs and 1 blocks/GPU (256^3 cells per block). The two scenarios are shown in Figure 3.5.

3.3.2 CROR test case

To test the new capabilities of WALBERLA, which now supports large-scale simulations of moving complex geometries on CPUs and GPUs, we set up the industrial test case of a counter-rotating open rotor (CROR).

We already saw in Figure 3.4 and Figure 3.6, that the node-level performance of a similar setup shows good results. In the upcoming SCALABLE deliverable 2.4, we also show good performing strong scaling benchmark results of the CROR test case on LUMI-C (CPU) and JUWELS-Booster (GPU).

In Figure 3.7 we see the Q-criterion of the flow field around the counter-rotating open rotors. This simulation is run on JUWELS Booster on 36 NVIDIA A100 GPUs for two hours. The simulation domain is split into 36 blocks with 256^3 cells per block, resulting in an overall count of 603,979,776 cells. The picture is taken after 480,000 time steps, which corresponds to 0.21 s in real-time. The simulation is run on a uniform grid with a resolution of 0.003m and a Reynolds number of 4640.94. The rotors are rotating counter-wise with a speed of 73.8 rad/s.

With this application we can show, that we enabled the efficient movement/rotation of complex geometries in the WALBERLA framework by the utilization of the PSM.

Figure 3.7: Q-criterion of the CROR after 0.21s real time. The Q-criterion is colored with the velocity magnitude.

3.4 Sparse data structure for moving domains

The sparse data structure approach we implemented is not very suitable for moving geometries. Without using the PSM, we run into two problems. We already mentioned the first problem in [section 3.1](#), that if the geometry moves, some boundary cells are converted to fluid cells. In this case, a reconstruction of the PDF values of these values is needed. This can be a complex procedure and can lead to instabilities, and more problematical in the scope of this project, to performance issues. The second problem of the sparse data structure with moving geometries is, that for every movement, the two list data structures, the `PDF list` and the `index list` (see Deliverable 5.1) have to be adapted. This is very performance-critical and is also hard to parallelize on accelerators such as GPUs. As far as we know, there is no literature for a sparse LBM handling complex moving domains.

Therefore, we choose the approach of the PSM to handle the complex moving domain and to avoid the need for PDF reconstruction. However, as the PSM handles every cell as a mix of fluid and boundary cells, one can not save memory or increase performance by not storing / computing boundary cells. So we can run the PSM on the sparse data structure, which means that we can run simulations with complex moving domains with the sparse LBM. However, we can not benefit from the speed-up of the sparse structure, as we have to store and compute all cells. This results in ending up with a porosity of 1.0 on the whole domain, which means, as shown in [Figure 2.1](#), that the sparse / indirect-addressing data structure is always worse than the dense / direct-addressing LBM.

We proved the functionality of the implemented sparse data structure for complex domains with three test cases. The first one was the LAGOON case, which is a highly turbulent large-scale application. The sparse LBM can run this simulation, but can not benefit from its strengths, as there are too few boundary cells in this setup. The next application was the artificial riverbed. Here, the simulation domain consists of two different areas. The particle bed is a highly porous media, where the sparse data structure can show its strength. The flow over the particles on the other side is a fluid-only area, where it is more worth utilizing the dense data structure. Therefore, we build a hybrid data structure, that can choose the structure of a WALBERLA block based on its porosity, to get maximum performance and minimum memory consumption. The third case was a blood flow through an artery, which resulted in a very sparse domain with block porosities around 0.15, which was again very beneficial for the sparse data structure.

Further, we extended the WALBERLA framework by the capability of complex moving domains. This was achieved by utilizing the PSM method. We show the integration of the PSM into the code generation of *lbmpy*, so that we can run simulations with the PSM with all kinds of stencils, collision models, streaming patterns and more.

We also showed, how to efficiently handle the movement/rotation of the geometry by a special geometry field and an interpolation kernel. We observed good node-level performance for the PSM and the rotation kernel on CPU and GPU. Lastly, we presented the counter-rotating open rotor industrial test case to show the functionality of the newly implemented capabilities of complex moving domains.

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